

Current Practices in Emission Measurement in the Dutch Asphalt Sector: Insights from the InnovA58 Test Section

Emission measurement has become an important topic in the Dutch asphalt sector as the industry advances towards warm mix technologies, higher recycling rates, and the use of alternative binders. These developments support climate and circularity goals, yet they also introduce new uncertainties regarding occupational exposure and broader environmental impact. Reliable field data are therefore essential for understanding emissions that arise during production, paving, service life, and eventual disposal, and for ensuring that innovations align with long term sustainability objectives.

This contribution outlines the protocol commonly used in the Netherlands to monitor emissions during asphalt production and paving. The protocol focuses on volatile organic compounds, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, aldehydes, and dust. Measurements rely on personal air sampling combined with stationary methods, supported by calibration procedures and laboratory analysis. This framework provides insight into exposure levels for workers and enables comparison with occupational limits. The InnovA58 test section provides a complementary material level perspective. A multi phase approach was used to analyze emissions associated with high reclaimed asphalt content and the use of rejuvenators in the lab. Gas chromatography mass spectrometry and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy were applied to both individual binder ingredients and full asphalt mixtures. The study showed that rejuvenator related emissions mainly occur at temperatures above 160°C and are characterized by aldehydes and hydrocarbons formed during heating. Reducing the production temperature can reduce these emissions significantly. This research also points to a broader challenge for future sustainable binders/ additives for asphalt. When novel components are introduced into a binder/ asphalt system, their molecular signatures must first be mapped and calibrated to allow quantification, and these data should be linked to established assessment practices for emissions. Such integration is essential for comparing new materials with conventional benchmarks and for guiding responsible adoption of innovative solutions in the Dutch asphalt sector.